

Supporting Information for:

Fiumera, A.C. 2024 Experience Matters: Evidence for genetic variation in male allocation to sequential mating events in *Drosophila melanogaster*. *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*

PROPORTION OF PRODUCTIVE MATINGS

Table S1. Test for effect of genotype by mating experience interaction on the proportion of productive matings. Models were fit using `glmer()` including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, GENOTYPE*MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects and BLOCK and MATING_EXP were fixed effects. Total sample size was 357 matings.

Model 1: <code>glmer(RED_EYE ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE))</code>				
Model 2: <code>glmer(RED_EYE ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1+GENOTYPE:MATING_EXP))</code>				
d.f.	LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
6	-84.796	-	-	-
7	-81.602	1	6.39	0.011

Table S2. Summary of Wald tests for the effect of mating experience on proportion of productive matings analyzed separately for each genotype. Models using `glmer()` failed to converge, likely due to the high proportion of males that ultimately mated. Therefore, the models were fit using `glm.cluster()` including BLOCK, MATING_EXP and `cluster(ID)` for repeated measures.

Genotype	Chi-squared value	Degrees of freedom	P-value
Line 332	351.3	2	< 2.2 x 10⁻¹⁶
Line 336	880.6	2	< 2.2 x 10⁻¹⁶
Line 358	0.19	2	0.91
Line 377	992.8	2	< 2.2 x 10⁻¹⁶
Line 379	320.4	2	< 2.2 x 10⁻¹⁶
Line 391	1039.4	2	< 2.2 x 10⁻¹⁶
Line 392	335.0	2	< 2.2 x 10⁻¹⁶
Line 796	522.7	2	< 2.2 x 10⁻¹⁶

Table S3. Tests for the effect of genotype on the proportion of productive matings analyzed separately for the different levels of mating experience. Models were fit using glmer() including GENOTYPE, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects and BLOCK was a fixed effect.

Model 1: glmer(RED_EYE ~ BLOCK + (1 ID))					
Model 2: glmer(RED_EYE ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + (1 GENOTYPE))					
Mating	d.f.	LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
First	3	-14.20	-	-	-
	4	-32.27	1	36.13	1.8 x 10⁻⁹
Second	3	-14.06	-	-	-
	4	-14.06	1	0	0.999
Third	3	-9.50	-	-	-
	4	-23.05	1	27.10	1.9 x 10⁻⁷

SPERM COMPETITIVE ABILITY (*P1* and *P1'*)

Table S4. Tests for the genotype by mating experience interaction affecting the proportion of offspring sired by the experimental male (*P1*). Models were fit using glmer() function with family = binomial, including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, GENOTYPE*MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects. Total sample size of 181 matings.

Model 1: glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID))							
Model 2: glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID) + (1+GENOTYPE:MATING_EXP))							
# parameters	AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
6	1554.6	1573.8	-771.3	1542.6	-	-	-
7	1414.2	1436.6	-700.1	1400.2	1	142.4	<2.2x10⁻¹⁶

Table S5. Tests for the effect of mating experience on the proportion of offspring sired by the focal male (*P1*) analyzed separately for each genotype. Models were fit using the glmer() function with family = binomial, including MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. ID was a random effect.

Model 1: glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + (1 ID))								
Model 2: glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 ID))								
Genotype	# par.	AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
332	3	182.8	186.1	-88.4	176.8	-	-	-
	5	184.3	189.8	-87.2	174.3	2	2.52	0.28
336	3	258.2	261.7	-126.1	252.2	-	-	-
	5	211.7	217.6	-100.8	201.7	2	50.52	1.1 x 10⁻¹¹
358	3	179.4	183.0	-86.7	173.4	-	-	-
	5	113.1	119.2	-51.5	103.1	2	70.3	5.4 x 10⁻¹⁶
377	3	153.3	156.9	-73.7	147.3	-	-	-
	5	155.7	161.6	-72.8	145.7	2	1.67	0.433
379	3	259.8	263.4	-126.9	253.9	-	-	-
	5	259.8	265.7	-124.9	249.8	2	4.02	0.133
391	3	183.4	186.8	-88.7	177.4	-	-	-
	5	160.0	167.7	-76.0	152.0	2	25.3	<2.2x10⁻¹⁶
392	3	140.3	141.8	-67.2	134.3	-	-	-
	5	55.3	57.7	-22.7	45.3	2	89.0	<2.2x10⁻¹⁶
796	3	406.3	410.2	-200.2	400.3	-	-	-
	5	230.3	236.8	-110.2	220.3	2	180.	<2.2x10⁻¹⁶

Table S6. Tests for the effect of genotype on the proportion of offspring sired by the focal male (*P1*) analyzed separately for each level of mating experience. Models were fit using glmer() function with family = binomial, including GENOTYPE, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects.

Model 1: glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + (1 ID))								
Model 2: glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + GENOTYPE + (1 ID))								
Mating	# par.	AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
FIRST	3	510.6	517.8	-252.3	504.6	-	-	-
	4	505.7	515.3	-248.9	497.7	1	6.9	0.0087
SECOND	3	270.7	277.1	-132.3	264.7	-	-	-
	4	272.0	280.5	-132.0	264.0	1	0.69	0.41
THIRD	3	175.1	180.0	-84.5	169.1	-	-	-
	4	176.4	182.9	-84.2	168.4	1	0.69	0.41

The results from the analyses of *P1'* are similar to *P1* although 1 fewer genotype shows a significant effect of mating experience and 1 fewer mating experience level shows an effect for genotype.

Table S7. Tests for the genotype by mating experience interaction affecting the proportion of offspring sired by the experimental male (*P1'*). Models were fit using glmer() function with family = binomial, including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, GENOTYPE*MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects.

Model 1: glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID))							
Model 2: glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID) + (1+GENOTYPE:MATING_EXP))							
# parameters	AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
6	1395.5	1413.7	-691.8	1383.5	-	-	-
7	1270.3	1291.6	-628.2	1256.3	1	127.2	<2.2x10 ⁻¹⁶

Table S8. Tests for the effect of mating experience on the proportion of offspring sired by the focal male (*P1'*) analyzed separately for each genotype. Models were fit using the glmer() function with family = binomial, including MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. ID was a random effect.

Model 1: glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + (1 ID))								
Model 2: glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 ID))								
Genotype	# par.	AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
332	3	182.8	186.0	-88.4	176.8	-	-	-
	5	184.3	189.6	-87.2	174.3	2	2.5	0.28
336	3	216.2	219.3	-105.1	210.2	-	-	-
	5	193.6	198.8	-91.8	183.6	2	26.6	1.7x10 ⁻⁶
358	3	88.5	90.6	-41.2	82.5	-	-	-
	5	87.6	91.2	-38.8	77.6	2	4.9	0.087
377	3	146.9	150.2	-70.4	140.9	-	-	-
	5	149.3	154.7	-69.6	139.3	2	1.6	0.44
379	3	256.3	259.6	-125.1	250.1	-	-	-
	5	256.7	262.1	-123.3	246.7	2	3.6	0.17
391	3	157.6	159.9	-75.8	151.6	-	-	-
	5	127.0	130.9	-58.5	117.0	2	34.6	3.1x10 ⁻⁸
392	3	132.0	133.2	-63.0	126.0	-	-	-
	5	48.9	50.9	-19.45	38.9	2	87.1	<2.2 x 10 ⁻¹⁶
796	3	377.8	381.5	-185.9	371.8	-	-	-
	5	200.4	207.0	-95.4	190.7	2	181	<2.2 x 10 ⁻¹⁶

Table S9. Tests for the effect of genotype on the proportion of offspring sired by the focal male (*P1*) analyzed separately for each level of mating experience. Models were fit using `glmer()` function with family = binomial, including GENOTYPE, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects.

Model 1: <code>glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + (1 ID))</code>								
Model 2: <code>glmer(cbind(V2R,V2W)~ BLOCK + GENOTYPE + (1 ID))</code>								
Mating	# par.	AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
FIRST	3	460.4	467.0	-227.2	454.4	-	-	-
	4	460.8	469.7	-226.4	454.8	1	1.6	0.21
SECOND	3	254.3	260.3	-124.2	248.3	-	-	-
	4	256.3	264.3	-124.2	248.3	1	0	1
THIRD	3	165.2	169.5	-79.6	159.2	-	-	-
	4	167.2	172.9	-76.6	159.2	1	0	1

MALE-INDUCED REFRACTORINESS TO REMATING

Table S10. Test for effect of genotype by mating experience interaction on male-induced refractoriness to remating. Models were fit using the `coxme()` function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, GENOTYPE*MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE, and ID were random effects. Total sample size was 368 matings and 181 events.

Model 1: <code>glmer(RED_EYE ~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID))</code>			
Model 2: <code>glmer(RED_EYE ~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID) + (1+GENOTYPE:MATING_EXP))</code>			
LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
-1006.61	-	-	-
-997.48	21	18.26	0.6326

Table S11. Test for effect of mating experience on male induced refractoriness to remating. Models were fit using the `coxme()` function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE, and ID were random effects.

Model 1: <code>glmer(RED_EYE ~ BLOCK + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID))</code>			
Model 2: <code>glmer(RED_EYE ~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID))</code>			
LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
-1014.7	-	-	-
-1006.61	2	16.116	0.00032

Table S12. Test for effect of genotype on male induced refractoriness to remating. Models were fit using the `coxme()` function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE, and ID were random effects.

Model 1: <code>glmer(RED_EYE ~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP) + (1 ID)</code>				
Model 2: <code>glmer(RED_EYE ~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID))</code>				
	LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
	-1006.61	-	-	-
	-1006.61	1	0.0041	0.9491

Table S13. Post-hoc comparisons for male-induced refractoriness to remating compared between levels of mating experience. Models were fit using `coxme()` function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE, and ID were random effects. Tukey tests were performed using `glht()` function. Total sample size was 368 and 181 events were observed. Shown in Figure 3A.

Comparison	Estimate	Error	Z value	P-value
Second - First	0.08113	0.1696	0.478	0.8809
Third - First	-0.65377	0.1974	-3.312	0.0026
Third - Second	-0.73490	0.2070	-3.551	0.0011

MALE FERTILITY (red-eyed V1 + red-eyed V2)

Table S14. Test for genotype by mating experience interaction affecting the number of offspring sired by a male (male fertility) using offspring from both vial 1 and vial 2. Models were fit using `lmer()` function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, GENOTYPE*MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects. The number of offspring was cube root transformed to improve the fit to normality. The total sample size was 333 matings.

Model 1: <code>lmer(RED_OFF_CR ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE))</code>					
Model 2: <code>lmer(RED_OFF_CR ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1+GENOTYPE:MATING_EXP))</code>					
	d.f.	LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
	7	-354.52	-	-	-
	8	-354.52	1	0	1

Table S15. Test for effect of mating experience on the number of offspring sired by a male (male fertility) using offspring from both vial 1 and vial 2. Models were fit using lmer() function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects. The number of offspring was cube root transformed to improve the fit to normality.

Model 1: lmer(REDOFF_CR ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + (1 GENOTYPE))				
Model 2: lmer(REDOFF_CR ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE))				
d.f.	LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
5	-398.95	-	-	-
7	-354.52	2	88.859	< 2.2 x 10 ⁻¹⁶

Table S16. Test for the effect of genotype on the number of offspring sired by a male (male fertility) using offspring from both vial 1 and vial 2. Models were fit using lmer() function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects. The number of offspring was cube root transformed to improve the fit to normality.

Model 1: lmer(REDOFF_CR ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP)				
Model 2: lmer(REDOFF_CR ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE))				
d.f.	LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
6	-359.09	-	-	-
7	-354.52	1	7.1478	0.007506

Table S17. Post-hoc comparisons for number of offspring sired by a male (male fertility) using offspring from both vial 1 and vial 2 between different levels of mating experience. The model was fit using the lmer() function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects. Shown in Figure 3B.

Comparison	Estimate	Std. Error	Z Value	P-value
Second - First	-0.783	0.091	-8.59	< 1.0 x 10 ⁻⁵
Third - First	-0.820	0.090	-9.10	< 1.0 x 10 ⁻⁵
Third - Second	-0.037	0.096	-0.38	0.92

Figure S1. Male fertility in vials 1 and 2 for each of the genotype and mating experience combinations. The genotype by mating experience interaction was not significant so no statistical tests are reported.

MALE FERTILITY (red-eyed in V1)

The results when using offspring from only vial 1 are similar although the effect of genotype is only marginally significant in vial 1.

Table S18. . Test for genotype by mating experience interaction affecting the number of offspring sired by a male (male fertility) using offspring from vial 1. Models were fit using the lmer() function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, GENOTYPE*MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects. The number of offspring was square root transformed to improve the fit to normality. Total sample size was 333 matings.

Model 1: lmer(V1R_SQ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE))				
Model 2: lmer(V1R_SQ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1+GENOTYPE:MATING_EXP))				
d.f.	LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
7	-542.77	-	-	-
8	-542.14	1	1.26	0.2616

Table S19. Test for effect of mating experience on the number of offspring sired by a male (male fertility) using offspring from both vial 1 and vial 2. Models were fit using the lmer() function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects. The number of offspring was square root transformed to improve the fit to normality.

Model 1: lmer(V1R_SQ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + (1 GENOTYPE))				
Model 2: lmer(V1R_SQ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE))				
d.f.	LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
5	-555.22	-	-	-
7	-542.77	2	24.909	3.9 x 10⁻⁶

Table S20. Test for the effect of genotype on the number of offspring sired by a male (male fertility) using offspring from both vial 1 and vial 2. Models were fit using the lmer() function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects. The number of offspring was square root transformed to improve the fit to normality.

Model 1: lmer(V1R_SQ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP)				
Model 2: lmer(V1R_SQ~ BLOCK + (1 ID) + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE))				
d.f.	LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
6	-544.36	-	-	-
7	-542.77	1	3.1794	0.07457

MALE MATING SPEED

Table S21. Test for genotype by mating experience interaction affecting male mating speed. Models were fit using the `coxme()` function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, GENOTYPE*MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects. Total sample size is 368 and the number of events is 357.

Model 1: <code>coxme((TTM1_COX, MATE1_EVER) ~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID))</code>			
Model 2: <code>coxme((TTM1_COX, MATE1_EVER) ~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID) + (1+GENOTYPE:MATING_EXP))</code>			
LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
-1785.9	-	-	-
-1773.7	21	24.54	0.2677

Table S22. Test for effect of genotype on male mating speed. Models were fit using the `coxme()` function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects.

Model 1: <code>coxme((TTM1_COX, MATE1_EVER) ~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 ID))</code>			
Model 2: <code>coxme((TTM1_COX, MATE1_EVER) ~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID))</code>			
LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
-1786.3	-	-	-
-1785.9	1	0.6534	0.4189

Table S23. Test effect of mating experience on male mating speed. Models were fit using the `coxme()` function including GENOTYPE, MATING_EXP, BLOCK and ID for repeated measures. GENOTYPE and ID were random effects.

Model 1: <code>coxme((TTM1_COX, MATE1_EVER) ~ BLOCK + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID))</code>			
Model 2: <code>coxme((TTM1_COX, MATE1_EVER) ~ BLOCK + MATING_EXP + (1 GENOTYPE) + (1 ID))</code>			
LogLik	d.f.	Chi-squared	P-value
-1788.1	-	-	-
-1785.9	2	4.2893	0.1171

